

ACTIVITIES IN THE BUKHARA PEOPLE'S SOVIET REPUBLIC TO PROTECT THE HEALTH OF THE POPULATION

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Annotation. *This article provides a scientific analysis of the state of healthcare in the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic, formed in 1920-1924 after the overthrow of the Emirate of Bukhara and the measures taken in this area.*

Key words: *BPSR, "Bukhara Varajasi", "Bukhara Akhbori", Council of People's Ministers, Khavzolsihat, FRG, Mollaria.*

In September 1920, in Bukhara, one of the ancient centers of civilization in Central Asia, the despotic emir power was overthrown and the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic (BPSR) was created. Although the young Government of the republic is engaged in a fierce struggle to end the economic, socio-political and cultural backwardness inherited from the Emirate, the ongoing military operations (i.e., the independence movement) throughout the young country have led to a peaceful and prosperous economic life, which put an end to centuries of backwardness did not allow. On the contrary, most of the five million population of the republic (according to some sources, three and a half million), suffering from hunger and financial difficulties, suffered from epidemics. The ecological situation in Bukhara, dry, dusty, hot weather and drinking water are the main problems that caused the spread of smallpox, mumps, plague, ulcers, genital warts. In particular, Isaev, a doctor sent from the Center to the Republic of Bukhara for the prevention of infectious diseases, made up the majority of the population with Bukhara malaria, listed many symptoms associated with aging, whiteness of the skin and lips, aging of the film on the inside of the eyelashes, swelling of the spleen.

Literary critic Sherahli Turdiev writes about Bukhara students sent to study in Germany in 1922-1923: "Bahouddin Amin is an Uzbek from Bukhara who came to Germany with a serious illness. He was treated for two months at Professor Schelling's private clinic in Germany. Now he is studying successfully".[1]

Not only smallpox and malaria, but also plague, suffocation, ulcers and sweating affected people. In some provinces, field work in the same season was delayed due to the illness of the majority of the able-bodied population. "This year (1922) the harvest in the Karshi district is in full swing, but the entire population is dying in the desert from fever. There are no healthy people in the meeting" [2] the Bukhara Akhbori newspaper reported.

Of course, the government headed by F.Khodzhayev has taken appropriate measures to restore public health and prevent diseases. By order of the Chairman of the Council of People's Ministers, medicines for the treatment of malaria were distributed free of charge in the villages. A special regulation on the "General Directorate of Health Care" has been developed, it was signed personally by F.Khodzhaev. The charter included such issues as the

supply of medicines, the opening of infectious points, the creation of military sanatoriums, the construction of pharmacies, the creation of children's health resorts. Medicines were purchased at the expense of exported cotton, wool, doodle, sweets, intestines. Medicines were purchased at the expense of exported cotton, wool, doodle, sweets, intestines. The medical center received various medicines and medical supplies purchased in Germany. These include two polar stations (Farage's office) and a number of pharmacies that will open in front of hospitals. In 1923, 1,500 needles and needles arrived (slightly less than 2.5 packs per kg) [3].

These drugs are of great importance due to the beginning of the mollaria (epidemiological) season. The cost of medicines is more than 40,000 soums in gold coins. From February to November 1923, 4 wagons of hospital equipment and medicines worth 200,000 soums were delivered from the German Republic to Bukhara alone.

It should be noted that on the recommendation of the Ministry of Health to purchase medicines and hospital equipment from Germany and the head of Government F. Khodjaeva, the populist leader, agreed to purchase medicines and hospital equipment in exchange for exported Bukhara goods. He was a man who deeply understood that the main wealth of the Republic is the health of the people, who loved his people and his country with all his heart.

In the Bukhara Republic, attention was paid to the opening of paramedic stations and hospitals. During August-September 1923, hospitals and paramedic stations were opened in such districts and cities as Sherabad, Nurata, Derband, Shakhrisabz, Karki. "Measures have been taken to open hospitals with 30 beds each in the Karshi, Karmanin and Shakhrisabz regions, where the sanitary checkpoint is located" [5]. At the end of 1923, the Council of People's Ministers of the Bukhara Republic issued a special decree prohibiting the cultivation of harmful crops, poppy, cannabis, opium, etc., damaging the health of the population and morally and ethically corrupting the population. Conferences on the prevention of infectious diseases were organized in most districts. Consultations are open at mobile medical centers in the districts of Eastern Bukhara. A pharmacy has been opened in Old Bukhara at a discounted price at the expense of the state. "By 1924, the Institute of Tropical Diseases, 5 hospitals and 2 outpatient clinics were functioning in the republic" [6].

Thus, during the short, four-year history of the Bukhara Republic, the Government paid serious attention to healthcare, pursued a policy based on humane democratic principles, took practical measures against many epidemics and prevented large losses.

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